

Interoperable nanosafety data using semantic modeling and linked data knowledge graphs

Ammar Ammar, Chris T. Evelo and Egon L. Willighagen

Supplementary File 1

SPARQL queries used to summarize the content of the RDFied datasets

```

1 PREFIX bao: <http://www.bioassayontology.org/bao#>
2 PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
3 PREFIX dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
4
5 SELECT ?datasetLabel(COUNT(?ep) AS ?endpointCount)
6 WHERE {
7
8     ?dataset dcat:distribution ?datasetrdf.
9
10    {
11        ?datasetrdf rdfs:label ?datasetLabel.
12
13        ?bioassay bao:BAO_0000209 ?mg;
14                dct:source ?datasetrdf.
15
16        ?mg bao:BAO_0000208 ?ep.
17        ?ep a bao:BAO_0000179.
18
19        FILTER(STR(?datasetLabel) != "Dataset 3")
20    }
21    UNION
22    {
23        VALUES ?datasetLabel {"Dataset 3"@en}
24        ?datasetrdf rdfs:label ?datasetLabel.
25
26        ?ep rdf:type bao:BAO_0002138.
27    }
28 }
29 GROUP BY ?datasetLabel
30 ORDER BY ?datasetLabel

```

Listing 1 The SPARQL query used to retrieve the number of measured endpoints per source dataset from the NanoLinks-KG knowledge graph

```
1 PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
2 PREFIX dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
3
4 SELECT ?datasetLabel (COUNT(DISTINCT ?material) AS ?
   materialCount)
5 WHERE {
6
7     ?dataset dcat:distribution ?datasetrdf.
8     ?datasetrdf rdfs:label ?datasetLabel.
9
10    ?material dct:source ?datasetrdf;
11             dct:type ?materialType.
12 }
13 GROUP BY ?datasetLabel
14 ORDER BY ?datasetLabel
```

Listing 2 The SPARQL query used to retrieve the number of materials per source dataset from the NanoLinks-KG knowledge graph

```
1 PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
2 PREFIX dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
3
4 SELECT ?datasetLabel (COUNT(DISTINCT ?materialType) AS ?
   materialTypeCount)
5 WHERE {
6
7     ?dataset dcat:distribution ?datasetrdf.
8     ?datasetrdf rdfs:label ?datasetLabel.
9
10    ?material dct:source ?datasetrdf;
11             dct:type ?materialType.
12 }
13 GROUP BY ?datasetLabel
14 ORDER BY ?datasetLabel
```

Listing 3 The SPARQL query used to retrieve the number of material types per source dataset from the NanoLinks-KG knowledge graph

```

1 PREFIX bao: <http://www.bioassayontology.org/bao#>
2 PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
3 PREFIX dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
4
5 SELECT ?datasetLabel (COUNT(DISTINCT ?assayType) AS ?
   assayTypeCount)
6 WHERE {
7   ?dataset dcat:distribution ?datasetrdf.
8   ?datasetrdf rdfs:label ?datasetLabel.
9
10  ?bioassay dct:source ?datasetrdf.
11
12  ?bioassay rdf:type bao:BAO_0000015;
13             rdf:type ?assayType.
14
15  FILTER (?assayType NOT IN (bao:BAO_0000015))
16 }
17 GROUP BY ?datasetLabel
18 ORDER BY ?datasetLabel

```

Listing 4 The SPARQL query used to retrieve the number of assay types per source dataset from the NanoLinks-KG knowledge graph

```

1 PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
2 PREFIX npo: <http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/npo#>
3 PREFIX bfo: <http://www.ifomis.org/bfo/1.1/snap#>
4 PREFIX dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
5
6 SELECT ?datasetLabel (COUNT(DISTINCT ?materialQualityType )
   AS ?materialQualityTypeCount)
7 WHERE {
8
9     ?dataset dcat:distribution ?datasetrdf.
10    ?datasetrdf rdfs:label ?datasetLabel.
11
12    ?material dct:source ?datasetrdf;
13              dct:type ?materialType.
14
15    {
16        ?material npo:has_quality ?materialQuality.
17    }
18    UNION
19    {
20        ?material npo:has_part ?material_part.
21        ?material_part npo:has_quality ?materialQuality.
22    }
23
24    ?materialQuality rdf:type ?materialQualityType.
25
26    FILTER (?materialQualityType NOT IN (bfo:Quality))
27 }
28 GROUP BY ?datasetLabel
29 ORDER BY ?datasetLabel

```

Listing 5 The SPARQL query used to retrieve the number of nanomaterial quality types per source dataset from the NanoLinks-KG knowledge graph

```

1 PREFIX bao: <http://www.bioassayontology.org/bao#>
2 PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
3 PREFIX dcat: <http://www.w3.org/ns/dcat#>
4
5 SELECT ?datasetLabel (COUNT(DISTINCT ?species) AS ?
   speciesCount)
6 WHERE {
7
8   ?dataset dcat:distribution ?datasetrdf.
9   ?datasetrdf rdfs:label ?datasetLabel.
10
11  ?bioassay dct:source ?datasetrdf;
12            rdf:type bao:BAO_0000015;
13            bao:BAO_0000205 ?assayFormat.
14
15  ?assayFormat bao:BAO_0002004 ?cellLine.
16
17  ?cellLine bao:BAO_0090006 ?species.
18
19  ?species a bao:BAO_0000551;
20           a ?speciesType.
21
22  FILTER (?speciesType NOT IN (bao:BAO_0000551))
23 }
24 GROUP BY ?datasetLabel
25 ORDER BY ?datasetLabel

```

Listing 6 The SPARQL query used to retrieve the number of species per source dataset from the NanoLinks-KG knowledge graph

```

1 PREFIX bao: <http://www.bioassayontology.org/bao#>
2 PREFIX dct: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
3
4 SELECT ?gene_species (COUNT(DISTINCT ?gene_id) AS ?geneCount)
5 WHERE {
6
7     {
8         SELECT ?gene_id ?gene_species WHERE{
9             ?gene a bao:BAO_0000582;
10             dct:identifier ?gene_id.
11             BIND("All species" AS ?gene_species)
12         }
13     }
14     UNION
15     {
16         SELECT ?gene_id ?gene_species WHERE{
17             ?gene a bao:BAO_0000582;
18             dct:identifier ?gene_id.
19             FILTER(regex(?gene_id, "ENSG"))
20             BIND("Human" AS ?gene_species)
21         }
22     }
23     UNION
24     {
25         SELECT ?gene_id ?gene_species WHERE{
26             ?gene a bao:BAO_0000582;
27             dct:identifier ?gene_id.
28             FILTER(regex(?gene_id, "ENSMUSG"))
29             BIND("Mouse" AS ?gene_species)
30         }
31     }
32     UNION
33     {
34         SELECT ?gene_id ?gene_species WHERE{
35             ?gene a bao:BAO_0000582;
36             dct:identifier ?gene_id.
37             FILTER(regex(?gene_id, "ENSRNOG"))
38             BIND("Rat" AS ?gene_species)
39         }
40     }
41     UNION
42     {
43         SELECT ?gene_id ?gene_species WHERE{
44             ?gene a bao:BAO_0000582;
45             dct:identifier ?gene_id.
46             FILTER(!regex(?gene_id, "ENSG"))
47             FILTER(!regex(?gene_id, "ENSMUSG"))
48             FILTER(!regex(?gene_id, "ENSRNOG"))
49             BIND("Unannotated" AS ?gene_species)
50         }
51     }
52 }
53 ORDER BY DESC(?geneCount)

```

Listing 7 The SPARQL query used to retrieve the number of unique genes in Dataset 3 from the NanoLinks-KG knowledge graph